

High-resolution mass spectrometry strategies for profiling fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products in environmental matrices

Vasileios D. Alampanos^{a,b}, Dimitra A. Lambropoulou^{a,b,*}

^a Laboratory of Environmental Pollution Control, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, GR-541 24, Greece

^b Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center, 10th km Thessaloniki-Thermi Rd, Thessaloniki, GR-570 01, Greece

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ABSTRACT

Fluorinated pesticides, particularly those having trifluoromethyl ($-CF_3$) substituents, are increasingly used in agriculture due to their high stability and efficacy. However, these characteristics lead to PFAS-like persistence, high environmental mobility, and formation of fluorinated transformation products (TPs) including residues such as trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) which may exhibit distinct chemical and toxicological properties. This review highlights how advances in LC-HRMS instrumentation, acquisition approaches, and data-processing tools expand the monitoring potential for fluorinated pesticides and their TPs in environmental matrices. Targeted LC-HRMS approaches for quantifying known pesticides are critically described, emphasizing key parameters, method settings, and quality-control requirements. Suspect and non-target screening methodologies are then examined as strategies that broaden analytical coverage to include predicted, database-derived, or previously unknown compounds. Laboratory-induced transformation studies are presented as essential complementary sources for generating TPs, providing HRMS data and mechanistic transformation pathways that significantly strengthen environmental screening and annotation confidence. Overall, LC-HRMS is moving toward a unified analytical framework capable of integrating target, suspect, and non-target workflows for comprehensive monitoring of known and unknown fluorinated pesticides TPs. The studies and methodologies summarized herein offer a conceptual and practical foundation for improved identification and TPs identification of fluorinated pesticides.

1. Introduction

1.1. Fluorinated pesticides and their regulatory classification

Over the past few decades, pest management practices in agriculture have evolved considerably, with fluorinated pesticides becoming increasingly predominant [1–3]. Initially accounting for only about 9% of the pesticide market at the beginning of the century, fluorinated pesticides now represent more than half of newly registered formulations, with nearly 70% of recently approved agrochemicals incorporating fluorine [1,2,4]. This sustained trend toward increased fluorination of pesticide active ingredients reflects the ability of fluorine incorporation, particularly the addition of a $-CF_3$ group to confer enhanced stability, lipophilicity, and bioavailability, biological properties that improve pesticide performance, durability and commercial competitiveness [1,2,5]. However, these same features also contribute

to environmental persistence and mobility, complicating degradation and removal processes. Therefore, the extensive use of fluorinated pesticides, particularly those containing trifluoromethyl ($-CF_3$) substituents, has raised growing concerns due to their persistence, potential transformation, and long-term environmental effects [1,2,5]. Structurally, many fluorinated pesticides share several physicochemical features with per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), including the presence of strong carbon–fluorine bonds that impart high thermal and chemical stability [3,4]. This structural overlap has contributed to their inclusion under certain PFAS regulatory definitions. Under the OECD definition, which classifies any substance containing at least one fully fluorinated methyl group ($-CF_3$) or perfluorinated methylene group ($-CF_2-$) as a PFAS, many widely used pesticides meet the criteria [6]. The more restrictive ECHA definition applied in the REACH PFAS restriction proposal similarly includes pesticides bearing perfluorinated methyl or methylene groups not directly bonded to hydrogen, oxygen, or

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* Corresponding author. Laboratory of Environmental Pollution Control, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, GR-541 24, Greece.

E-mail address: dlambro@chem.auth.gr (D.A. Lambropoulou).

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halogens [7]. These definitions illustrate that fluorinated pesticides are structurally aligned with regulated PFAS compounds which are linked to oxidative stress, endocrine disruption, impaired growth or reproduction in living organisms, and broader environmental harm [8].

Beyond their direct classification, fluorinated pesticides have attracted increasing attention because they act as indirect sources of persistent fluorinated pollutants through degradation, generating transformation products of broader concern. For example, they have recently been shown to be substantial environmental sources of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), a terminal and highly persistent transformation product formed through abiotic and oxidative transformation processes [9–12]. TFA, classified as a short-chain perfluoroalkyl substance, is now globally detected in a wide range of water matrices, including rivers, lakes, groundwater, and coastal marine systems. Consequently, the degradation of CF₃-containing agrochemicals represents a significant indirect source of TFA, further linking fluorinated pesticides to PFAS-related pollution [9–12]. Although fluorinated pesticides and conventional PFAS such as PFOA and PFOS share physicochemical features associated with fluorinated moieties, they differ fundamentally in their sources, intended uses, and environmental behavior. Conventional PFAS are primarily industrial chemicals characterized by high environmental stability and limited transformation, whereas fluorinated pesticides are intentionally applied agrochemicals that undergo diverse abiotic and biotic transformation processes, often generating multiple transformation products. Analytically, both compound classes present challenges related to trace-level detection and matrix effects; however, fluorinated pesticides pose additional complexity due to the co-occurrence of parent compounds and unknown transformation products, necessitating integrated target, suspect, and non-target LC–HRMS workflows.

Despite growing concerns, fluorinated pesticides remain in use, and new compounds continue to be introduced because of the properties that fluorination confers [4,13]. Within the European Union, numerous fluorinated active substances are still approved. Compounds with current authorizations extending beyond November 2025 include beflubutamid, flazasulfuron, flonicamid, fluopicolide, fluochloridone, flutianil, isoxaflutole, mefentrifluconazole, oxathiapiprolin,

penoxsulam, picolinafen, and trifloxystrobin, with several approvals extending into the late 2020s and early 2030s [14]. Their continued approval demonstrates that, even under the EU's precautionary regulatory framework, fluorinated pesticides still play a major role in agricultural practice, highlighting the challenge of balancing efficacy with concerns over environmental persistence and accumulation. Several compounds have been detected in foods across many EU countries. For example, according to PAN Europe's 2024 report, the most frequently detected PFAS active substances in EU-grown fruit & vegetables in 2021 included fluopyram, flonicamid and trifloxystrobin [15]. Other pesticides detected in monitoring programs include lambda-cyhalothrin, triflumuron, fluopicolide, sulfoxaflor, tau-fluvalinate, tetraconazole and cyflufenamid. Monitoring these compounds is essential to understand consumer exposure and improve regulatory oversight in agriculture [3]. In general, the monitoring of pesticide residues in food across the EU and EFTA (European Free Trade Association) is coordinated through the Multiannual Control Programs for Pesticide Residues (MACP), which assess compliance with maximum residue levels and supports consumer exposure assessments [16]. Although the MACP is updated annually and complemented by national monitoring programs, several authorized pesticides are absent from the most recent MACP monitoring list, despite their persistence and widespread use. Table 1 presents an overview of 66 PFAS-pesticides: 33 appear in the MACP list, 16 are included only in the working document SANCO/12745/2023 (but not monitored), and 17 are completely absent from EU monitoring schemes.

Naturally, many of these pesticides, including fludioxonil, fluopyram, trifloxystrobin, fluazinam, and flufenoxuron, have been repeatedly detected in environmental matrices [3,5,17–22]. Therefore, beyond food and agricultural monitoring, PFAS-pesticides are increasingly recognized within broader European environmental surveillance initiatives. Although they are not yet individually listed on the EU Water Framework Directive Watch List, they are considered emerging priority contaminants, and several PFAS-pesticides meet the criteria for substances requiring closer scrutiny due to their persistence, and mobility potential [23]. The European Drinking Water Directive (EU) 2020/2184 introduces requirements for monitoring pesticides groups in drinking

Table 1

Classification of 66 fluorinated pesticides based on their presence in MACP 2026–2028 and Working document SANCO/12745/2013.

Included in MACP Regulation 2026-28 (07 May 2025)		Included in Working Document SANCO/12745/2013 17-18 February 2025	Not Included in MACP Regulation 2026-28
Acrinathrin - C ₂₆ H ₂₁ F ₆ NO ₅	Haloxyfop incl. - R (Free acid) - C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ NO ₄	Chlorfluazuron - C ₂₀ H ₉ Cl ₃ F ₅ N ₃ O ₃	Beflubutamid - C ₁₈ H ₁₇ F ₄ NO ₂
Bifenthrin (sum of isomers)- C ₂₃ H ₂₂ ClF ₃ O ₂	Indoxacarb (sum) - C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₃ O ₇	Fluazinam - C ₁₃ H ₄ Cl ₂ F ₆ N ₄ O ₄	Benfluralin - C ₁₃ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₃ O ₄
Chlorfenapyr - C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrClF ₃ N ₂ O	Lambda-Cyhalothrin (sum) - C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ NO ₃	Fludioxonil metab. CGA 192155 - C ₈ H ₄ F ₂ O ₄	Cyclobutirifluram - C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₂ O
Cyflufenamid (sum of isomers) - C ₂₀ H ₁₇ F ₅ N ₂ O ₂	Lufenuron (sum of isomers) - C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ F ₈ N ₂ O ₃	Fluensulfone - C ₇ H ₅ ClF ₃ NO ₂ S ₂	Diflufenican - C ₁₉ H ₁₁ F ₅ N ₂ O ₂
Cyflumetofen (sum of isomers) - C ₂₄ H ₂₄ F ₃ NO ₄	Mefentrifluconazole - C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClF ₃ N ₃ O ₂	Flufenacet - C ₁₄ H ₁₃ F ₄ N ₃ O ₂ S	Flazasulfuron - C ₁₃ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₅ O ₅ S
Fipronil - C ₁₂ H ₄ Cl ₂ F ₆ N ₄ OS	Metaflumizone (sum of isomers) - C ₂₄ H ₁₆ F ₆ N ₄ O ₂	Fluopyram-Benzamide (M ₂₅) - C ₆ H ₆ F ₃ N O	Flumetralin - C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClF ₄ N ₃ O ₄
Fipronil sulfone - C ₁₂ H ₄ Cl ₂ F ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	Oxathiapiprolin - C ₂₄ H ₂₂ F ₅ N ₅ O ₂ S	Isoxaflutole - C ₁₅ H ₁₂ F ₃ NO ₄ S	Fluometuron - C ₁₀ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂ O
Flonicamid - C ₉ H ₆ F ₃ N ₃ O	Pyridalyl - C ₁₈ H ₁₄ Cl ₄ F ₃ NO ₃	Isoxaflutole diketonitrile-metabolite - C ₁₅ H ₁₂ F ₃ NO ₄ S ₄	Flurochloridone - C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ F ₃ NO
Flonicamid metab. TFNA - C ₇ H ₄ F ₃ NO ₂	Sulfoxaflor (sum of isomers) - C ₁₀ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₃ OS	Novaluron - C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₈ N ₂ O ₄	Flutolanil - C ₁₇ H ₁₆ F ₃ NO ₂
Flonicamid metab. TFNG - C ₉ H ₇ F ₃ N ₂ O ₃	Tau-Fluvalinate - C ₂₆ H ₂₂ ClF ₃ N ₂ O ₃	Oxyfluorfen - C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ NO ₄	Penoxsulam - C ₁₆ H ₁₄ F ₅ N ₅ O ₅ S
Fluazifop incl. P (free acid) - C ₁₅ H ₁₂ F ₃ NO ₄	Tefluthrin - C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClF ₇ O ₂	Penthiopyrad - C ₁₆ H ₂₀ F ₃ N ₃ OS	Picoxystrobin - C ₁₈ H ₁₆ F ₃ NO ₄
Flubendiamide - C ₂₃ H ₂₂ F ₇ IN ₂ O ₄ S	Tetraconazole - C ₁₃ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ F ₄ N ₃ O	Picolinafen - C ₁₉ H ₁₂ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂	Prosulfuron - C ₁₅ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₅ O ₄ S
Fludioxonil - C ₁₂ H ₆ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	Trifloxystrobin - C ₂₀ H ₁₉ F ₃ N ₂ O ₄	Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) - C ₂ HF ₃ O ₂	Pyroxsulam - C ₁₄ H ₁₃ F ₃ N ₆ O ₅ S
Flufenoxuron - C ₂₁ H ₁₁ ClF ₆ N ₂ O ₃	Triflumizole - C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ClF ₃ N ₃ O	Trifluralin - C ₁₃ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₃ O ₄	Tembotrione - C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ O ₆ S
Fluopicolide - C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₃ F ₃ N ₂ O	Triflumizole metab. FM-6-1 - C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ClF ₃ N ₂ O	Tritosulfuron - C ₁₃ H ₉ F ₆ N ₅ O ₄ S	Tembotrione metab. M ₅ - C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ O ₆ S
Fluopyram - C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClF ₆ N ₂ O	Triflumuron - C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClF ₃ N ₂ O ₃	Tritosulfuron metab. AMTT - C ₅ H ₅ F ₃ N ₄ O	Tetraniliprole - C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ N ₁₀ O ₂
Flutianil - C ₁₉ H ₁₄ F ₄ N ₂ OS ₂			Triflusaluron metab. IN-M ₇₂₂₂ - C ₅ H ₆ F ₃ N ₅ O

water, highlighting the need for harmonized surveillance capable of capturing both parent PFAS-pesticides and their TPs across environmental matrices [24]. Accordingly, PFAS-pesticides should undergo long-term monitoring under the EU Water Framework Directive to clarify their occurrence, sources, and transport into aquatic systems.

1.2. Fate and challenges in detecting fluorinated pesticides

Fluorinated pesticides reach environmental matrices through a variety of interconnected pathways following their application (Fig. 1). These include runoff from treated agricultural fields, leaching into groundwater, and transport via irrigation return flows, all of which contribute to their detection in surface waters and soils. Additional inputs may arise from wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluents, where parent pesticides or their TPs can persist due to incomplete removal during treatment processes [1,5,12,17,25–27]. PFAS pesticides may further be redistributed through spray drift, aerosolization, or particle-bound transport, leading to their redeposition onto both terrestrial and aquatic environments [28].

Many fluorinated pesticides also fall within the category of Persistent and Mobile Organic Compounds (PMOCs), substances capable of passing through natural and engineered treatment barriers and dispersing over long distances in aquatic systems. [29,30]. PMOCs and PFAS pesticides often occur at very low concentrations and may evade detection by conventional monitoring approaches, their reliable identification depends on high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and the use of target, suspect, and non-target screening workflows, which are essential for the comprehensive characterization of fluorinated pesticides [31, 32]. Beyond their parent structures, fluorinated pesticides frequently undergo a variety of abiotic (photolysis, oxidation, hydrolysis) and biotic processes that generate TPs [1,10,21,25,30,33–36]. Depending on environmental conditions such as sunlight, pH, and redox state, these reactions can yield TPs with altered polarity, distinct chromatographic behavior, and different ionization efficiencies, complicating their detection in LC–HRMS workflows [29–32]. These transformation pathways may also produce isomeric TPs, further increasing the need for high mass accuracy, detailed MS/MS interpretation, and advanced data-processing tools to confidently distinguish structurally similar species. In addition, many TPs retain fluorinated functional groups (e.g., –CF₃, –CF₂–), contributing to their persistence and mobility, and in some cases may exhibit equal or greater toxicity than the parent compound (see Section 3). Because parent pesticides and their multiple TPs can co-occur in environmental samples, often at low and variable

concentrations and thus their characterization requires integrated target, suspect, and non-target HRMS workflows to ensure reliable detection and structural elucidation [37].

Traditional analytical methods have relied on target analysis, in which predefined analytes are quantified using calibration standards. However, the increasing structural diversity of fluorinated pesticides and the vast variety of possible TPs have made suspect and non-target screening indispensable for comprehensive environmental monitoring. These approaches depend heavily on liquid chromatography coupled with LC–HRMS, which provides the mass accuracy, resolving power, and dynamic range required to detect and identify both known and unknown species in complex environmental matrices. Recent advances in HRMS instrumentations such as Orbitrap and quadrupole time-of-flight mass analyzers together with improvements in data-processing algorithms, now support integrated analytical workflows. These workflows facilitate the discovery of previously unreported TPs and enable the development of compound-specific databases and spectral libraries, an essential capability given the limited availability of analytical standards for fluorinated pesticides [31,32,37–39].

Focusing on the evolution of analytical instrumentation and data processing approaches and tools, the present review aims to highlight how recent advances in LC–HRMS methodologies may transform the identification and monitoring of PFAS pesticides and their TPs in environmental matrices. We outline representative target, suspect, and non-target workflows applied in environmental monitoring, and we summarize TP-formation studies that elucidate new TPs. Such studies, strongly favored by high-resolution mass spectrometry, are essential for improving our understanding of the environmental fate of PFAS pesticides and for supporting the development of reliable analytical databases which are the cornerstone of effective LC–HRMS based suspect and non-target screening approaches. Through this perspective, we offer a critical overview of analytical strategies used to identify, monitor, and characterize fluorinated pesticides and their TPs, emphasizing how the combined use of target, suspect, and non-target workflows together with TPs formation studies enhances our understanding of their environmental fate and contributes substantially to strengthening their monitoring potential Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Environmental fate of fluorinated pesticides.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the LC-HRMS analytical workflow for the determination of fluorinated pesticides.

2. LC-HRMS analytical workflows for fluorinated pesticides detection

2.1. HRMS analyzers, data acquisition and analytical features of pesticides

HRMS provides the analytical performance required to detect and identify fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products (TPs) in complex environmental matrices. The strong electron-withdrawing character of fluorinated moieties and the associated negative mass defect make high mass accuracy and resolving power essential for distinguishing fluorinated species from isobaric background ions. In addition, the frequent occurrence of low-abundance TPs necessitates acquisition strategies that enable broad analytical coverage and retrospective data analysis. Quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) instruments provide accurate-mass MS/MS combined with precursor selection, supporting structural elucidation and making them well suited for suspect and non-target screening. Orbitrap analyzers offer higher resolving power, which is particularly advantageous for distinguishing CF_3 -containing compounds that often overlap with non-fluorinated species in complex matrices. Hybrid ion trap-Orbitrap platforms further enhance TP characterization through MS^n capability and accurate-mass product-ion detection, generally improving selectivity and sensitivity for fluorinated pesticide analysis [27,31,32,40].

Data acquisition strategy strongly influences HRMS performance in fluorinated pesticide workflows. Full-scan acquisition enables retrospective screening of newly recognized compounds and TPs, while data-dependent acquisition (DDA) provides high-quality MS/MS spectra but may miss low-abundance features. In contrast, data-independent acquisition (DIA), including all-ion fragmentation (AIF), offers comprehensive fragmentation coverage at the expense of increased data complexity. Although DIA requires advanced data processing and careful false discovery rate control, it is particularly valuable in environmental samples where parent compounds and TPs co-occur across wide concentration ranges [41,42]. Recent studies highlight that combining acquisition modes can improve performance. For example, the integration of full-scan, all-ion fragmentation, and targeted MS^2 on Orbitrap platforms enhances target analysis, while full-scan with data-dependent MS^2 remains effective for non-target screening. Overall, reliable identification depends not only on acquisition strategy but also on robust data-processing workflows for filtering irrelevant signals and generating confident TP annotations [41,42]. These HRMS capabilities and parameters are particularly important when considering the structural and analytical characteristics of fluorinated pesticides. The presence of $-\text{CF}_3$ and $-\text{CF}_2$ groups strongly influences both chromatographic and mass-spectrometric behavior. These compounds often display a polarity-hydrophobicity imbalance: although CF_3 groups increase hydrophobicity, many of these compounds still contain polar functional groups, resulting in reduced retention or early elution in

reversed-phase LC systems. Their ionization efficiency, especially in electrospray ionization (ESI), is similarly influenced by fluorine substitution. Electron-withdrawing effects may suppress protonation while promoting the formation of adduct ions complicating feature annotation and quantification across matrices such as wastewater, surface waters, and soil extracts. In negative-mode MS/MS, fluorinated pesticides commonly yield diagnostic HF/ CF_2 losses and anionic fragments such as $[\text{CF}_3]^-$, $[\text{C}_2\text{F}_5]^-$, and $[\text{C}_3\text{F}_7]^-$. These patterns are analytically valuable, but extensive fluorination can also suppress fragmentation of the organic backbone, resulting in limited structural information and increasing reliance on high-quality, accurate-mass MS/MS data [43–45].

2.2. LC-HRMS target screening workflows

Target screening with LC-HRMS is the most reliable approach for quantifying known PFAS pesticides in environmental matrices, as it relies on analytical standards enabling full method validation (LOD, LOQ, recovery, precision). Identification is based on accurate-mass extracted ion chromatograms using narrow mass windows (± 2 –5 ppm), combined with high resolving power to minimize isobaric interferences which is an important aspect for fluorinated compounds with atypical mass defects. Data quality is ensured through standard criteria, including isotopic-pattern fit, retention-time consistency, signal-to-noise thresholds, and MS/MS confirmation. Efficient sample preparation and optimized instrumental parameters are essential to enhance recovery, reduce matrix effects, and ensure stable ionization and fragmentation. A key advantage of HRMS workflows is retrospective analysis, allowing re-examination of full-scan data as new compounds, transformation products (TPs), or regulatory targets emerge. This is particularly relevant for PFAS pesticides, for which new TPs are continuously reported. Despite these strengths, target workflows remain limited to compounds with available standards, leaving many PFAS pesticide TPs unquantified. In addition, fluorinated moieties (e.g., $-\text{CF}_3$) can affect ionization efficiency and promote adduct formation, complicating quantification, while isotopically labelled standards are not available for all analytes [31,37].

As summarized in Table 2, recent studies [32,46–51] demonstrate a high degree of methodological consistency in LC-HRMS target workflows, despite differences in analytical scope and environmental matrices. Common features include full-scan acquisition combined with data-dependent MS/MS, strict mass-accuracy criteria (< 5 ppm), isotopic-pattern verification, and retention-time matching. Most studies employ solid-phase extraction (SPE), commonly using hydrophilic-lipophilic balanced sorbents (e.g., Oasis HLB, Strata-X), often under acidic conditions to enhance analyte retention and reduce matrix effects. Such approaches support broad analyte coverage across a wide polarity range, which is essential for fluorinated pesticides that may exhibit diverse physicochemical properties. Instrumental parameters, including ionization mode, collision energy, and resolving power, are

Table 2
LC-HRMS target analysis workflows data of interest.

Number of Analytes/Contaminants	Number of PFAS or/and fluorinated pesticides Included	Matrix	HRMS System & Acquisition Mode -Ionization Mode/Resolution	LC-condition (Column, Gradient, Mobile Phases)	Sample Size	Sample Preparation Technique/Sorbents/sample's pH/Elution Solvents	Data Processing Software	Peak selection criteria	LOQ / RR% /RSD%	Key Findings after real sample analysis (DF and maximum concentrations)	Ref.
55 ECs (pharmaceuticals, Pesticides, PFAS)	4 (PFHpA, PFOA, PFOS, Fluometuron)	Wastewaters (Influent and effluent)	Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and 2E5 for MS2, ESI switching, 70000 for full scan and 35000 for ddMS2	Hypersil GOLD aQ column (50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.9 μm), MeOH and water both been acidified with 0.1 % (v/v) FA, Flow 200 μL/min; Injection 5 μL	250 mL and 100 mL (effluent and influent)	SPE, HLB Cartridges, pH = 3, MeOH	TraceFinder 4.1	peak shape (typical Gaussian), isotopic pattern (only a fit equal to or >90 %, retention time alignment in all screened samples), S/N > 5, peak area >10 ⁶ , mass tolerance <5 ppm, interpretation of MS/MS spectrum, tailing factor <0.5 at 10% height; retention-time window ±0.3 min	<1 ng/L, / 30-120 % / <20%	Fluometuron DF 88% in Effluents, max concentration 1304 ng/L	[32]
472 ECs (301 pesticides, 146 pharmaceuticals, 5 PCPs, 11 PFAs, 9 OPFRs)	11 PFAs, >30 fluorinated pesticides	Lake water (18 lakes in Greece)	Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and 2E5 for MS2, ESI switching, 70000 for full scan and 35000 for ddMS2	Hypersil GOLD aQ column (50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.9 μm), MeOH and water both been acidified with 0.1 % (v/v) FA, Flow 200 μL/min; Injection 5 μL	500 mL	SPE, HLB Cartridges, pH = 3, MeOH	TraceFinder 4.1	peak shape (typical Gaussian), isotopic pattern (only a fit equal to or >90 %, retention time alignment in all screened samples), S/N > 5, peak area >10 ⁶ , mass tolerance <5 ppm, interpretation of MS/MS spectrum, tailing factor <0.5 at 10% height; retention-time window ±0.3 min	N/A	Fluazifop-P-butyl (DF 5.6%, 3.9 ng/L), Fluquinconazole (DF 5.6 %, <LOQ), Flusilazole (DF 5.6 %, 0.5 ng/L), Lufenuron (DF 5.6%, 9.4 ng/L), Metaflumizone (DF 5.6%, 13.6 ng/L), Quinoxifen (DF 5.6 %, 31.6 ng/L), Trifloxystrobin (DF 5.6 %, 2.5), Triflumuron (DF 5.6 %, 0.8 ng/L)	[46]
756 Pesticides	Fipronil, Fludioxonil, Fluometuron, Flutolanil	Wastewaters (influent and effluent)	Bruker Maxis Impact Quadrupole-time-of-flight mass spectrometry (QTOF), full-scan, collision-induced dissociation (bbCID) acquisition mode (DIA), ESI+, ESI- (2 runs), 36,000–40,000	Accclaim RSLC C18 column (2.1 × 100 mm, 2.2 μm), (+ESI) (A) H ₂ O:MeOH (90:10) with 5 mM ammonium formate and 0.01 % FA and (B) MeOH with 5 mM ammonium formate and 0.01 % FA. For (-ESI), (A) H ₂ O:MeOH (90:10) with 5 mM ammonium acetate and (B) MeOH with 5 mM ammonium acetate.	100 mL	SPE, (200 mg Oasis HLB, 150 mg Isolute ENV+, 100 mg Strata-X-AW and 100 mg Strata-X-CV), pH = 6.5/methanol/ethyl acetate (1:1, v/v) containing 2% ammonia, followed by 2 mL of MeOH/ethyl acetate (1:1, v/v) containing 1.7% formic acid.	DataAnalysis 4.3, TASQ	Mass error <5 ppm (precursor & fragments), RT ±0.2 min, isotopic pattern match, in-house retention-time prediction model	<25 ng/L, / 57–120 % / <20%	Fipronil (DF/y, 30-100%, 19-241 ng/L) Fludioxonil (DF/y, 43-100%, 8.15-59.6 ng/L), Fluometuron (DF/y, 37,5-100%, 8.69-416 ng/L), Flutolanil (DF/y, 0-100%, 20.1-83.5 ng/L)	[47]
275 pesticides and 101 veterinary drugs	Diflubenzuron, Epoxiconazole, Florasulam, Flufenacet, Fluopicolide, Fluopyram, Fluoxastrobin, Flusilazole,	River water (Small streams and rivers across 10 EU countries)	Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and 5E4 for MS2, ESI switching, 70000 for full scan and 17500 for ddMS2	Accucore aQ C18 (100 × 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm); Water + 2% MeOH + 0.1% FA + 5 mM NH ₄ HCO ₂ (mobile phase A); Methanol + 2% H ₂ O + 0.1% FA + 5 mM NH ₄ HCO ₂ , Flow 300 μL/min; Injection 1 μL	200 mL	SPE (Oasis HLB 200 mg), pH 3; Elution 10 mL MeOH	TraceFinder 4.1, FreeStyle 1.1	Mass error <5 ppm; isotope match; 2+ MS ² fragments <5 ppm; RT drift <0.2 min; S/N > 3	<5 ng/L, / 70–130 % / <15%	Diflubenzuron (3% -), Epoxiconazole (DF 55%, 299.6 ng/L) Florasulam (DF 3%, 117.7 ng/L), Flufenacet (DF 41%, 926 ng/L), Fluopicolide (DF 17%, 6.6 ng/L), Fluopyram (DF 83%,	[48]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Number of Analytes/Contaminants	Number of PFAS or/and fluorinated pesticides Included	Matrix	HRMS System & Acquisition Mode -Ionization Mode/Resolution	LC-condition (Column, Gradient, Mobile Phases)	Sample Size	Sample Preparation Technique/Sorbents/sample's pH/Elution Solvents	Data Processing Software	Peak selection criteria	LOQ / RR% /RSD%	Key Findings after real sample analysis (DF and maximum concentrations)	Ref.
	Pyroxsulam, Tetraconazole									250.2 ng/L), Fluoxastrobin (DF 7%, 6.4 ng/L), Flusilazole (3% -), Pyroxsulam (3% -), Tetraconazole (DF 17%, 5.9 ng/L)	
71 pesticides	Cyhalofop-butyl, Cyhalothrin, Fipronil, Flumethrin, Fluvalinate	Surface water & sediment	Orbitrap Exploris™ 120, Full-scan, DDA, three-injection strategy for moderately polar (ESI+), polar (ESI+), and polar (ESI-) compounds, 60000 for full scan and 15000 for ddMS2	Luna C18 (15.0 cm × 0.21 cm, 3 μm), 0.1% FA and 5 mM NH ₄ HCO ₂ in Milli-Q water (A) and 0.1% formic acid and 5 mM NH ₄ HCO ₂ in MeOH (B).	250 mL (water), 1 g sediment	water: SPE (Strata-X, 200 mg, pH not adjusted, methanol)/ sediments: citrate buffered QuEChERS (dSPE with PSA and C18 for moderately polar compounds, SLE with a McIlvaine-EDTA buffer followed by SPE with Strata-X for polar compounds	TraceFinder 4.1	Mass accuracy <5 ppm (precursor & fragments); RT ±0.2 min; isotope/adduct grouping; TraceFinder manual confirmation	0.15-3 ng/L, / 38-104%/ <30%	43 pesticides detected in water; 59 in sediment; multi-injection LC-HRMS increases coverage; data used for ecological risk assessment (RQ), (Fluvalinate, DF 3%, 164.28 ng/L)	[49]
99 pesticides (polar analytes)	Acrinathrin, Bifenthrin, Cyfluthrin, Cyhalofop-butyl, Cyhalothrin, Diflufenican, Fipronil, Flumethrin, Fluvalinate, Oxyfluorfen, Quinoxifen, Transfuthrin, Trifluralin	Surface water	QTOF MS (Triple TOF 5600+, AB Sciex), Full-scan, IDA (DDA), ESI+, ESI- (2 runs), 30000 for TOF MS scan and 1500 for product ion	Acquity HSS T3 (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm), (+ESI) (A) 0.1 % FA in H ₂ O and (B) ACN. For (-ESI), (A) NH ₄ F in water (B) MeOH	250 mL	SPE, Strata-X, 200 mg, pH not adjusted, methanol	Analyst 1.7, Peak View 1.2	Mass error <5 ppm; isotopic-pattern match; MS/MS fragment confirmation	<6 ng/L, / N/A	Diflufenican detected frequently (e.g., DF 65% in DNP), maximum concentration: 161 ng/L	[50]
519 ECs (169 parent, 67 pesticides TPs, 283 urban ECs)	>50 fluorinated pesticides and TPs (e.g. (Fipronil, Flazasulfuron, Flonicamid, Fludioxonil, Flufenacet, Fluopicolide, Fluopyram, Flutolanil, Penoxsulam, Picoxystrobin, Prosulfuron, Pyroxsulam, Tembotrione, Trifloxystrobin, Triflumizole, Tritosulfuron and TPs)	Groundwater	Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap, Full-scan, DDA, ESI switching, 140000 for full scan and 17500 for ddMS2	C18 column Atlantis T3 (3 μm, 3.0 × 150 mm), 0.1% FA in Water/0.1% FA in MeOH	60 mL	Vacuum-assisted evaporation concentration	TraceFinder 4.1, in-house R Scripts	Mass error <5 ppm, Intensity threshold, isotopic fit, retention-time accuracy	<10 ng/L	33 of 169 pesticides, 30 of 67 pesticide TPs, 42 of 283 urban ECs (Flufenacet TPs -ESA 51 ng/L and OXA 5,1 ng/L)	[51]

typically optimized to maximize sensitivity and reproducibility, particularly for low-abundance compounds. These shared elements provide a strong analytical basis and enable comparability across studies. Anagnostopoulou et al. introduced a comprehensive multi-residue LC–HRMS method for 55 contaminants including three PFAS and fluometuron in wastewater influent and effluent [32]. Fluometuron appeared in more than half of the influent samples, reaching a peak level of 1406 ng/L in 2021. In the effluent, its detection frequency rose to 88%, with a maximum concentration of 1304 ng/L, suggesting that the compound is not being effectively removed. Rigorous data-quality controls (Gaussian peak shape; isotopic-pattern fit $\geq 90\%$; RT alignment; S/N > 5 ; peak area $> 10^6$; mass tolerance < 5 ppm; MS/MS interpretability; tailing factor < 0.5 ; RT window ± 0.3 min) underpin confidence in the target analyte results. The use of TraceFinder for data processing reflects a modern HRMS workflow applicable to routine monitoring. In a subsequent large-scale application, the same analytical framework was applied to 18 Greek lakes, screening hundreds of emerging contaminants, including numerous fluorinated pesticides [46]. Although detection frequencies were generally low, multiple fluorinated compounds were identified and quantified (quinoxifen, metaflumizone, lufenuron, fluzifop-P-butyl, flusilazole, triflumuron quinoxifen, metaflumizone) across different lakes, highlighting their persistence in surface waters influenced by agricultural activities.

A large-scale target LC–HRMS workflow was reported by Rousis et al., who implemented a broad-scope screening method covering 756 pesticides and related TPs and metabolites in wastewater influent and effluent [47]. The study included several fluorinated pesticides of interest, such as fipronil, fludioxonil, fluometuron and flutolanil making it highly relevant for evaluating HRMS target capabilities. Extracts were analyzed using a Bruker Maxis Impact QTOF operated in broadband collision-induced dissociation (bbCID) mode that is a full-scan operation mode, enabling simultaneous acquisition of precursors and fragment ions in a single injection. Importantly, several fluorinated pesticides exhibited high detection frequencies and notable concentration ranges across the seven-year monitoring period, highlighting both the widespread presence and the variable environmental persistence of fluorinated pesticides in wastewater systems. This study demonstrates the suitability of high-resolution QTOF platforms combined with bbCID acquisition for reliable target detection of fluorinated pesticides in complex matrices, and underscores the importance of multi-sorbent SPE strategies and RT-prediction tools in enhancing screening confidence.

Similarly, Casado et al. conducted one extensive LC–HRMS based monitoring campaigns across Europe, analyzing river waters from 29 small waterways across 10 EU countries using a robust target Orbitrap-based target workflow enabling the screening of 275 pesticides and 101 veterinary drugs, including 10 CF₃-substituted or fluorinated pesticides. [48]. All sampled streams were contaminated with pesticides and, in most cases, veterinary drugs. In total, 103 different pesticides were identified across sites. The study also detected several non-authorized pesticides including the fluorinated fungicide flusilazole along with 23 other substances not approved in the EU. Contamination levels were often substantial: the maximum combined pesticide concentration reached 94.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$, corresponding to a mixture of 70 different pesticides in a single sample. Furthermore, European regulatory standards were exceeded in at least one substance in 13 samples, indicating ecotoxicological concern. Among CF₃-containing pesticides, flufenacet (DF 41%, up to 926 ng/L), fluopyram (DF 83%, 250.2 ng/L), epoxiconazole (DF 55%, 299.6 ng/L), and florasulam (DF 3%, 117.7 ng/L) were most notable, while fluopicolide, fluoxastrobil, and tetraconazole were detected sporadically at ng/L levels. These findings underscore the importance of harmonized analytical workflows for large-scale environmental assessments.

Soriano et al. applied a versatile Orbitrap based LC–HRMS target workflow to monitor 71 pesticides across water and sediment matrices by adopting a multi-injection strategy improving the detection of compounds with varying polarity and physicochemical properties [49]. 43

pesticides were detected in water and 59 in sediments. Among the fluorinated compounds included in the target list, flufenacet was sporadically detected (DF 3%, 164.28 ng/L). Peris et al. applied a targeted LC–HRMS approach using a QTOF platform (TripleTOF 5600+) to monitor 99 polar pesticides in surface waters collected from two major Spanish wetland ecosystems [50]. Among detected fluorinated pesticides, diflufenican exhibited particularly high prevalence and reached a maximum concentration of 161 ng/L. Finally, in an comprehensive study, Kiefer et al. applied an extensive LC–HRMS target method to 519 emerging contaminants, consisting of 169 parent pesticides, 67 pesticide TPs, and 283 urban organic micropollutants, in groundwater. More than 50 fluorinated pesticides and fluorinated TPs were included in the target list, covering compounds such as fipronil, flazasulfuron, flonicamid, fludioxonil, flufenacet, fluopicolide, fluopyram, flutolanil, penoxsulam, picoxystrobin, prosulfuron, pyroxsulam, tembotrione, trifloxystrobin, triflumuron, tritosulfuron, and multiple fluorinated TPs [51]. The method achieved LOQs below 10 ng/L, supporting detection of 33 out of 169 parent pesticides, 30 out of 67 pesticide TPs, and 42 out of 283 urban ECs, including high-priority fluorinated TPs such as flufenacet-ESA (51 ng/L) and OXA (5.1 ng/L). Across the reviewed studies, this methodological consistency translates into robust and comparable analytical performance, enabling reliable detection of fluorinated pesticides across diverse environmental matrices. The widespread occurrence of these compounds at ng/L levels further confirms their environmental persistence and relevance. While both Orbitrap and QTOF platforms demonstrate comparable real-world performance, these findings collectively highlight that current LC–HRMS target workflows are sufficiently mature to support routine monitoring, while still requiring complementary approaches to address the limited coverage of transformation products.

2.3. Suspect and non-target screening workflows

While target LC–HRMS workflows enable high-confidence quantification of known pesticides, they are restricted to compounds for which analytical standards exist. Herein, we first summarize key aspects of suspect and non-target approaches and then examine screening strategies for identifying fluorinated pesticides and their TPs, which extend detection beyond predefined analyte lists and allow discovery of unexpected contaminants. In suspect screening, suspect compounds are predefined from scientific literature, structural databases (e.g., PubChem, ChemSpider, MassBank, mzCloud), regulatory databases (e.g., EU Watch List, EPA CompTox/DSSTox, OECD), or predicted transformation lists. These suspects are searched within HRMS data based on accurate mass, isotopic pattern, retention-time behavior, and MS/MS fragmentation. Structural elucidation is supported by knowledge-based and reaction-based resources (e.g., EAWAG-BBD) and in silico tools such as Mass Frontier, BioTransformer, enviPath, Meteor Nexus, and SIRIUS/CSI: FingerID. When available, retention-time prediction using QSRR-based models further supports candidate ranking. This approach is particularly effective for fluorinated pesticides, where transformation products can often be anticipated from known parent compounds. By contrast, non-target analysis proceeds without predefined candidate lists. Identification begins with feature extraction from full-scan data, followed by prioritization based on chromatographic behavior, reproducibility, and environmental relevance. Because fluorinated compounds exhibit characteristic mass defects and predictable isotopic patterns, mass-defect filtering and heteroatom-based prioritization are commonly applied. Structural annotation is supported by databases such as METLIN, MassBank, mzCloud, ChemSpider, and PubChem, while standardized identifiers (e.g., SMILES, InChI, CAS, PubChem CID, DTXSID) ensure consistency across platforms. While NTA enables broad contaminant discovery, its effectiveness for fluorinated pesticides is often lower compared to suspect screening, which benefits from prior knowledge of parent compounds and transformation pathways [37,39,52,53].

Table 3
Suspect and non-target screening approaches.

Analysis Type (Suspect/Non-target/Both)	Number of Suspects (Fluorinated-suspect compounds)	Matrix	HRMS System & Acquisition Mode -Ionization Mode/Resolution	Data Processing Tools/Software	Databases/Libraries Used	Feature Prioritization & Filtering Criteria	Confirmation and Identification	Transformation-Prediction Tools Used	Identification Confidence (Schymanski Levels)	Key Findings/Notes	Ref.
Suspect screening	386 pesticides (including >30 fluorinated) and 181 TPs	Surface waters	Q Exactive HF Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and SE5 for MS2, ESI switching, 120000 for full scan and 30000 for ddMS2	Shinyscreen (R-package), MetFrag	SWISSPEST list, LUXPEST suspect list; HSDB TPS list; NORMAN-SLE; PubChem; CompTox; MoNA/MassBank	Pre-screening with Shinyscreen, coarse $m/z \pm 0.5$ Da; fine $m/z \pm 2.5$ ppm; RT tolerance ± 0.5 min; XIC ± 0.001 Da; MS^1 intensity $\geq 1 \times 10^5$; S/N > 3	Retention-time alignment; MS^2 fragment ion matching; MetFrag candidate scoring; MoNA spectral consistency; RT match ± 0.2 min	EAWAG-BBD biotransformation rules; PubChem TP associations; HSDB TP dataset	level 1: 31 compounds; level 2a: 5 compounds; level 3: 205 compounds	Parent pesticides elute later; TPs elute earlier (more polar); 20 compounds quantified; retention-trend validation (Epoxiconazole, max C: 29,941 ng/L, Tritosulfuron max C: 18,782 ng/L (level 1))	[55]
Suspect screening	181 pesticides (including fluorinated pesticides e.g., diflufenican, fluometuron, fluopyram)	Freshwater streams & rivers (Melbourne region)	Xevo G2 QToF, MS^c , DIA, ESI \pm	UNIFI	ChemSpider	Two-stage suspect filtering: Filter-1 (mass accuracy, isotope match), Filter-2 (fragment match via MS^c), peak shape & retention-time	Lock-mass leucine-enkephalin standard; procedural blanks; reproducibility checks; MS/MS fragment-ion matching	Not explicitly applied	level 1: 5 compounds (fluopyram, fluopicolide, penthiopyrad, pydiflumetofen, selamectins); majority level-2/level 3 tentative	21 detections, (8 fluorinated pesticides) Bistrifluron, Fluazifop-P-butyl, Flumioxazin, Fluopicolide, Fluopyram, Isopyrazam, Penthiopyrad, Pydiflumetofen	[57]
Suspect screening (complementary to target screening)	2500 PMOCs (Dichlofluanid, fluometuron, etc.)	Wastewaters (influent, effluent)	Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and 2E5 for MS2, ESI switching, 70000 for full scan and 35000 for ddMS2	TraceFinder 4.1	in-house database created from literature sources and open-access databases	Peak area $> 10^6$, Isotopic pattern $> 90\%$, RT drift threshold, Peak shape filtering	Schymanski level 3 (formula match), Schymanski level 2b (fragment-supported match), Manual formula correction, Literature-supported fragment matching	Not explicitly applied (Fragment support relied on literature-reported spectra and available MS/MS interpretation within TraceFinder)	level 2b, level 3	14 (2b) and 56 (3) additional suspects identified on top of 55 targets	[32]
Suspect screening (complementary to target screening)	223 pesticides + 1033 TPs (>1100 suspects, not covered by the target list)	Groundwater	Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap, Full-scan, DDA, ESI switching, 140000 for full scan and 17500 for ddMS2	Compound Discoverer 2.1, RStudio R, scripts, ProteoWizard, R packages	database Eawag-Soil	RT alignment, peak intensity, S/N > 10, isotope pattern, MetFrag scoring	MS/MS fragment-ion matching, RT relativeness,	EAWAG-Soil TP pathway database, MetFrag CL 2.4.2	level 1-3 (Fipronil-TP RPA 106681 max 120 ng/L and TP RPA 200761 max 71 ng/L, Fludioxonil TP CGA 192155 max 200 ng/L, Fluxapyroxad (BAS 700 F)-TP CSAA798670 max 13 ng/L and (BAS	22 level 1 suspects confirmed; 13 TPs newly reported for the first time in groundwater, TP R471811 detected in all samples up to 2700 ng/L - TPs often exceeded parent pesticides	[51]

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Analysis Type (Suspect/Non-target/Both)	Number of Suspects (Fluorinated-suspect compounds)	Matrix	HRMS System & Acquisition Mode -Ionization Mode/Resolution	Data Processing Tools/Software	Databases/Libraries Used	Feature Prioritization & Filtering Criteria	Confirmation and Identification	Transformation-Prediction Tools Used	Identification Confidence (Schymanski Levels)	Key Findings/Notes	Ref.
Non-target screening (complementary to target screening)	Not applicable (feature-driven, not list-driven)	Surface water & sediment	Orbitrap Exploris™ 120, Full-scan, DDA, three-injection strategy for moderately polar (ESI+), polar (ESI+), and polar (ESI-) compounds, 60000 for full scan and 15000 for ddMS2 of the four most intense ions	Compound Discoverer® (workflow “Environmental w Stats Unknown ID w Online and Local Database Searches”)	ChemSpider, mzCloud	Peak-picking and integration, blank-subtraction, isotope/adduct grouping, RT alignment, feature clustering	MS/MS fragment confirmation; database score; RT	Not explicitly applied	700 F)-TP CSCD465008) max 64 ng/L level 2a	Detected additional non-target contaminants (primary compounds and TPs) beyond target list	[49]
Non-target (complementary to target screening)	Not applicable (feature-driven, not list-driven)	Lake water	Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap; Full-scan, DDA, AGC target of 1.0E6 for MS1 and 2E5 for MS2, ESI switching, 70000 for full scan and 35000 for ddMS2	Compound Discoverer® (workflow “Environmental w Stats Unknown ID w Online and Local Database Searches”)	ChemSpider, mzCloud	Mass-defect filter (-0.200-0 mDa), peak shape, intensity normalization, blank subtraction, mass error < 5 ppm	Isotopic fit, fragment-ion interpretation, mzCloud match (>70%)	Not explicitly applied	level 2a	18 additional NTA compounds detected	[46]
Non-target	Not applicable (feature-driven, not list-driven)	Fish muscle tissues	Orbitrap Exploris 240; Full-scan, DDA, ESI-,two injection approach, 1. only full-scan in 240000 resolutions, 2. 120000 for full scan and 45000 for ddMS2 (full-scan and DDA ddMS2)	MATLAB scripting for FBU-specific screening and filtering algorithm & fragment matching	ChemSpider and PubChem	Diagnostic HF neutral loss; characteristic fragments (C ₆ H ₃ F ₂ ⁻ & C ₇ H ₄ ONF ₂ ⁻); isotopologue rules; retention-time alignment; elimination of >99.98% irrelevant ions	Blank controls & reagent blanks; reference-standard confirmation for 4 fluorinated benzoylurea (FBU) pesticides; retention-time verification; isotopic & mass-error consistency	Logical transformation pathways inferred from precursor FBUs, structure similarity, ion-neutral losses	level 1 (confirmed) for 4 FBUs; level 2b & level 3 for analogues and TPs	4 original FBUs, 8 FBU analogues, and 11 FBU-TPs (e. g. hexaflumuron, lufenuron, chlorfluzuron, fluazuron, forchlorfenuron, and chlorobenzene)	[58]

In practice, suspect and non-target screening workflows are supported by dedicated LC–HRMS data-processing environments that enable feature detection, alignment, deconvolution, and annotation. Commonly used tools include mzMine, XCMS, OpenMS, MetAlign, MSConvert (ProteoWizard), CAMERA, and enviMass for pre-processing, followed by platforms such as Compound Discoverer®, MassHunter®, UNIFI®, MetaboScape, MetFrag, and Sirius-CSI:FingerID for formula assignment, fragment interpretation, and candidate ranking [39,53,54]. The results are typically reported using the standardized identification confidence evaluation scale introduced by Schymanski et al. [54]. In cases where a reference standard is not available, the quantification of the identified TP may be conducted using a semi-quantification approach derived from the calibration equation of the parent pesticide [51,55]. In Europe, much of the advancement and harmonization of such workflows has been strongly supported by the NORMAN network, which maintains and updates suspect lists, mass spectral databases, and retrospective screening recommendations, enabling researchers to systematically examine HRMS data against continually expanding lists of pesticides and their TPs [56]. Complementary initiatives such as BP4NTA and its Study Reporting Tool (SRT) further support standardization by promoting transparent reporting, reproducibility, and comparability across studies [57]. Key advantage of these approaches is the retrospective value of full-scan HRMS data, allowing re-analysis as new transformation products emerge, an aspect particularly critical for fluorinated pesticides with poorly characterized transformation pathways. Selected representative suspect and non-target LC–HRMS workflows for fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products are summarized in Table 3.

Following the above, Krier et al. implemented a LC–HRMS based suspect screening workflow to uncover pesticides and their TPs in surface waters using a Q Exactive HF Orbitrap system [55]. The suspect lists consisted of 386 parent pesticides (including >30 fluorinated pesticides) and 181 TPs compiled from SWISSEST, LUXPEST, NORMAN-SLE, HSDB, and CompTox inventories. Candidate detection proceeded through a hierarchical screening approach: initial MS¹-level pre-screening using the ShinyScreen R package yielded 6440 potential hits based on coarse *m/z* filtering (± 0.5 Da), isotope pattern fit, and chromatographic consistency. Subsequent fragmentation-based validation using MetFrag refined the data to 265 unique compounds, demonstrating the essential importance of MS² evidence for minimizing false positives. Prioritization and QC criteria included MS¹ intensity $\geq 10^5$, S/N > 3, RT tolerance ± 0.5 min, and XIC matching ± 0.001 Da, resulting in 31 level 1, 5 level 2a, and 205 level 3 identifications. A clear chromatographic pattern emerged: parent pesticides eluted later than TPs supporting TP assignments through retention-time/polarity logic. This interpretation was further corroborated using transformation-rule engines (EAWAG-BBD), TP links from PubChem and HSDB, and structure-based filtering. Finally, 20 compounds were quantified (level 1), including epoxiconazole (max 29,941 ng/L) and tritosulfuron (max 18,782 ng/L), demonstrating substantial environmental occurrence of fluorinated pesticides. Importantly, the authors emphasized the use of standardized chemical identifiers (InChI, InChIKey, SMILES, CAS RN, PubChem CID, DSSTox DTXSID), ensuring standardization across platforms and libraries, enabling robust cross-database identification and supporting long-term data reuse. The study adhered to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) by depositing suspect lists, annotations, and spectral evidence into open repositories, thereby facilitating future retrospective data processing, confidence upgrading as new spectra become available, and analytical harmonization across laboratories.

Similarly, Serasinghe et al. applied a suspect-screening workflow using passive samplers deployed in freshwater streams and rivers of the Melbourne region to capture time-integrated pesticide contamination [58]. Sampling was performed using Chemcatcher® (SDB-XC sorbent) and POCIS (HLB sorbent) devices, after which extracts were analyzed on a Waters Xevo G2 QToF operated with MS^c data-independent acquisition and polarity switching (ESI±). Suspect identification was supported by UNIFI software with candidate assignment against ChemSpider resources.

A structured two-stage suspect-filtering strategy was implemented: (i) Filter-1 applied exact mass and isotope-pattern constraints, and (ii) Filter-2 added fragment-ion validation using MS^c MS/MS spectra, along with peak-shape and RT matching. Quality control included lock-mass correction with leucine-enkephalin, procedural blanks, and reproducibility assessment via multiple exposures. Identification assignments, resulting in five level-1 confirmations (fluopyram, fluopicolide, penthiopyrad, pydiflumetofen, selamectin), with the remaining detections classified as level-2 or level-3 suspects. In total, 21 pesticides were detected, including eight fluorinated compounds such as bistrifluron, fluzafop-P-butyl, flumioxazin, fluopicolide, fluopyram, isopyrazam, penthiopyrad, and pydiflumetofen several of which had not been previously reported in Australian aquatic environments. These findings demonstrate the added value of integrating sampling strategies with suspect screening for improved environmental assessment. Compared with Orbitrap full scan/DDA workflows, the Xevo G2 QToF in MS^c DIA mode provides continuous fragmentation for broader MS/MS coverage, despite lower resolving power. Reproducible fragment matching and passive-sampling integration still enabled comparable detection and strong identification performance.

Kiefer et al. implemented a suspect screening approach as a complementary tool to a target analysis method, explicitly designed as a methodological reference model for pesticide and TP identification in groundwater [51]. Using a Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap (ESI±, Full-scan/DDA, 140,000 MS¹ resolution, 17,500 for ddMS²), 223 parent pesticides and 1033 TPs were screened. The data-processing workflow integrated multiple layers: raw data conversion with ProteoWizard/MSConvert, automated feature extraction in Compound Discoverer, and custom R scripts for refined filtering, deduplication, and intensity-threshold processing, enabling systematic handling of >10⁶ raw mass features. Candidate structures were annotated using in-silico fragmentation prediction (MetFrag), complementing isotopic-pattern matching, retention-time plausibility, and spectral-library comparisons against MassBank and ChemSpider. This approach proved especially effective for fluorinated pesticides and their TPs, whose –CF₃/–CF₂– motifs exhibit characteristic mass defects and simple monoisotopic patterns. In total, 27 pesticides and TPs (levels 1–3) were confidently assigned, including TPs of nicosulfuron, fipronil, bixafen, and fluxapyroxad, several of which had not been previously reported in groundwater. High-confidence identification of fluorinated pesticide TPs was achieved (Table 3), demonstrating that fluorinated pesticides undergo transformation and may yield products with even greater environmental persistence than parent compounds. Taken together, the HRMS acquisition, open-format conversion, R-based processing, and in-silico prediction form a reproducible, transparent workflow for large-scale pesticide screening. The shared code, databases, scripts, tools, and spectral resources support standardized FAIR workflows. It is important to emphasize that in modern environmental LC–HRMS workflows it is increasingly recommended that target analysis be complemented with suspect- or non-target-based screening. In this direction, Anagnostopoulou et al. [32] employed suspect screening as a complementary step to the target-quantification workflow to identify PMOCs and additional xenobiotics not included in the target list. The suspect analysis was performed using a 2500-compound literature-based in-house list. Candidate prioritization involved peak-shape evaluation, isotopic-pattern fit, retention-time matching, and MS/MS fragmentation assessment within TraceFinder®, resulting in additional level 2b and level 3 assignments beyond the target results, highlighting the value of hybrid approaches in environmental monitoring.

Moving to indicative non-target workflows, Soriano et al. applied a fully feature-driven non-target analysis as a complementary extension to the target LC–HRMS workflow, enabling the detection of emergent contaminants not included in predefined analyte lists [49]. Features were processed in Compound Discoverer® (“Environmental w Stats Unknown ID”), applying peak-picking, retention-alignment, blank-subtraction, de-adducting, and feature clustering. MS² fragmentation data supported

structural approximation through ChemSpider and mzCloud spectral resources. Confidence assignment resulted mainly in level 3 formula-matches and a smaller number of level 2 tentative identifications, although no additional fluorinated pesticides or TPs were detected. Similarly, Anagnostopoulou et al. applied non-target screening as a complementary layer to an extensive target LC–Orbitrap HRMS analysis [46]. Using Compound Discoverer 3.2 with the “Environmental with Stats Unknown ID with Online and Local Database Searches” workflow, they identified 18 additional non-target contaminants that were not included in the target acquisition list. However, NTA did not reveal any new fluorinated pesticides or PFAS beyond those detected by target analysis. These findings suggest that, under typical conditions, suspect screening provides higher detection efficiency for fluorinated pesticides compared to NTA, even though NTA remains valuable for broadening the identification of emerging contaminants.

Nonetheless, methodological advances demonstrate the potential of optimized NTA strategies. Tang et al. applied a structured LC–Orbitrap–HRMS workflow for fluorinated benzoylureas (FBUs) in fish tissue, offering an approach that could be adapted to environmental water and soil matrices [59]. The workflow combined two complementary data-processing strategies. First, a MATLAB-based procedure applied class-specific filters, including fluorine-related mass defects, C–F bond isotopologue behavior, diagnostic HF neutral loss, and characteristic fragments such as $C_6H_3F_2^-$ and $C_7H_4ONF_2^-$. This reduced ~395,000 detected ions to 82 precursor features. Second, MS/MS spectra, neutral-loss pathways, retention time, and structural consistency were manually evaluated to refine the identifications. This strategy enabled the confident identification of 4 FBUs at level 1, 8 structural analogues, and 11 FBU transformation products at levels 2b–3, demonstrating high selectivity and strong structural discrimination. Although developed for fish tissue, the analytical logic is matrix-independent. Halogen-aware filtering, mass-defect prioritization, isotopologue checking, and transformation-network reconstruction are directly transferable to environmental NTA workflows. This study shows how NTA can become more targeted in practice by applying data-reduction rules based on the chemical behavior of the contaminant class of interest, rather than relying on predefined suspect lists. Although suspect screening currently offers higher detection yields for fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products, optimized fluorine-specific NTA can enhance the discovery of previously undetected compounds, especially when standards are unavailable, fragmentation data are limited, or transformation pathways remain unclear. Thus, suspect and non-target HRMS approaches play complementary roles in pesticide monitoring: the former supports efficient identification of known or expected compounds, while the latter broadens exploratory contaminant discovery.

3. The role of laboratory induced transformation studies and the contribution of HRMS: TPs identifications and analytical potential

As evident from the previous subsection, only a limited number of TPs of fluorinated pesticides have been detected in environmental matrices. This is likely due to their altered physicochemical properties, lower abundance, increased polarity, different elution, reduced ionization efficiency, and weaker fragmentation coupled with the lack of commercially available TP reference standards. The situation is further complicated by the fact that transformation often produces isomeric and isobaric species that cannot be differentiated by exact mass alone. In this direction, laboratory-induced degradation studies play a pivotal role: by simulating hydrolytic, oxidative, or photolytic under controlled conditions, they generate authentic TP candidates that can be structurally elucidated using HRMS and subsequently used to inform environmental screening. Transformation of CF_3 -substituted pesticides produces a structurally diverse array of hydroxylated, oxidized, dealkylated, and ring-cleavage derivatives. Consequently, confident TP identification relies on accurate-mass MS/MS, fragment-ion interpretation, retention-

time reasoning, and the use of predictive tools and in-silico fragment simulation. This strategy may establish a robust basis for holistic transformation-product databases that can substantially enhance both suspect and non-target screening approaches (Table 4) [37,64].

In a recent study, the transformation pathways of the fluorinated sulfonylurea herbicides trifloxysulfuron (TFS) and prosulfuron (PSF) were investigated under five oxidative water-treatment processes: hydrolysis, chlorination, ozonation, UV photolysis, and UV/ H_2O_2 advanced oxidation comprehensively mapping their degradation kinetics and TP profiles [60]. A dual-HRMS approach was used: a Q-Exactive Orbitrap for chlorination and photolysis experiments, and a Bruker Impact HD QTOF for hydrolysis and ozonation. Data interpretation followed two complementary workflows, incorporating mass-defect filtering, isotopologue modeling, precursor–fragment matching, and characteristic neutral-loss recognition (including SO_2). As a result, 16 TFS TPs and 9 PSF TPs were identified, revealing different transformation routes (Fig. 3). TFS showed extensive structural modification including sulfonylurea cleavage, pyrimidine hydroxylation and chlorination (notably at C5), SO_2 -loss-driven rearrangements, and in some cases ring-opening of the heterocycle. PSF exhibited more limited reactivity, dominated by sulfonylurea cleavage, with oxidative hydroxylation occurring primarily under OH^\bullet -based conditions. Several TPs retained their fluorinated moieties, forming persistent fluorinated residues with distinct mass-defect signatures. For TFS, TP454, TP472, TP400, TP374, TP342, TP331, and TP257 preserved the CF_3 group; for PSF, TP252, TP284, TP268, TP452, and TP436 retained the trifluoropropyl unit. These fluorinated TPs are structurally stable and environmentally relevant due to their persistence and limited oxidative susceptibility.

Mekonnen et al. investigated the photodegradation pathways of the fluorinated fungicide fluopyram (FLP) in aqueous solution under UV-C irradiation (200–280 nm), identifying ten photoproducts through LC-MS/MS and Orbitrap HRMS analysis [61]. The study demonstrated rapid photolysis, with >90% degradation occurring within 3 h of UV-C exposure, while the compound remained stable under natural sunlight. The authors identified both previously reported PPs and seven newly described TPs, primarily arising from hydroxylation and lactam-based derivatives. Hydroxylated products included multiple dihydroxyl-FLP isomers (P9a–d), hydroxylimide species (P7a–b), and monohydroxyl- and trihydroxyl-lactam derivatives (P11 and P6), all supported by retention time behavior, isotopic distribution, diagnostic fragments, and ≤ 5 ppm mass-accuracy thresholds. Two additional products, P1 and P4, formed through rearrangement reactions via ethylene elimination (loss of $H_2C=CH_2$), demonstrating a mechanistically distinct pathway not involving direct hydroxylation. The study exploited fluorine-signature fragments (m/z 173 and 145), characteristic of the trifluoromethyl-benzamide substructure, as reliable MS/MS indicators of fluorine-containing residues. In a second fluopyram transformation study [62], degradation was examined in water under ozone-enhanced microbubble treatment (OMBT), providing an advanced oxidation scenario capable of generating extremely high $\cdot OH$ concentrations. OMBT proved markedly more efficient than ozonation alone or microbubbles alone, with complete FLP removal observed within ~40–60 min depending on initial concentration, demonstrating accelerated breakdown kinetics [62]. Using a hybrid ion trap–Orbitrap HRMS operated in positive ESI mode, three TPs (F1, F2, and F3) were structurally elucidated based on exact-mass accuracy, diagnostic fragment ions, and retention time. F1 ($C_{16}H_{12}F_6N_2O_2$) resulted from hydroxyl substitution on chlorine sites, F2 ($C_{16}H_9ClF_6N_2O_3$) represented further dual hydroxyl oxidation forming an imide derivative; and F3 ($C_8H_6F_3NO$) reflected amide-bond cleavage forming a small trifluoromethyl-containing aromatic fragment. All three retained fluorine, thereby remaining environmentally persistent fluorinated residues. All three transformation products retained fluorine, indicating continued environmental persistence. Toxicity predictions suggest that, although some TPs may exhibit reduced aquatic toxicity, changes in other endpoints and increased mobility may still raise environmental concerns. These studies show that common transformation pathways coexist with

Table 4
LC–HRMS based structural elucidation of selected fluorinated pesticide transformation products under laboratory induced transformation conditions.

Parent Pesticide (Abbreviation)	Number of TPs/metabolites	Identified TPs	Fluorinated TPs	Main transformations	Matrix/AOP Conditions	Sample Preparation & Cleanup	LC-instrument condition (Column, Mobile Phase, time)	MS System/Data acquisition Mode/Ionization Mode	Data processing/identification prioritization/software tools	Confidence Level	TP Environmental Relevance/Key Findings/Notes	Ref.
Trifloxysulfuron (TFS)	16 TPs	TP257, TP156, TP472, TP454, TP400, TP342, TP331, TP374, TP174, TP172, TP169, TP176, TP190, TP215, TP199, TP194	TP454, TP472, TP400, TP374, TP342, TP331, TP257, (7 TPs retain CF ₃ moiety)	Cleavage of sulfonylurea bond; pyrimidine hydroxylation & chlorination at C5; SO ₂ elimination rearrangement; ring-opening	oxidative water treatment processes: Hydrolysis, chlorination, ozonation, UV photolysis, OH• reactions	Direct injection after reaction; no SPE required	Kinetex Phenomenex F5 (150 × 2.1 mm) column; H ₂ O/MeOH + 0.1% FA; 10 µL injection volume	Q–Exactive Orbitrap (chlorination and photolysis TPs), ESI ± switching, Impact HD QToF (ozonation and hydrolysis)	Xcalibur 2.0 SR2, neutral loss recognition; mass defect filtering; retention alignment, precursor→fragment linking	levels 2–3, TP156, TP257 level 1, other 14 levels 2–3,	TP257 persistent across treatments; some TPs predicted to be more toxic than parent (e.g., TP169, TP190), TFS is more stable upon UV irradiation, chlorination rates are faster for TFS	[60]
Prosulfuron (PSF)	9 TPs	TP141, TP252, TP184, TP268, TP127, TP452 (isomers), TP436 (isomers), TP284	TP252, TP284, TP268 TP452, TP436 - retain trifluoropropyl	Sulfonylurea bond cleavage dominant; OH-driven hydroxylation of aryl-sulfonamide		Direct injection; stopped by NaOH to quench hydrolysis				level 1 for TP141 & TP252; level 2–3 others	TP141 & TP252 persist through all water treatment conditions; fluorinated residues may reach DWTP influent	
Fluopyram (FLP)	11 TPs	P1, P4, P6, P7a-b, P9a-d, P11	All 10 TPs retain the fluorinated moieties as shown by F-specific fragments	Hydroxylation, lactam formation, ethylene-elimination rearrangement	UV-C photolysis (200–280 nm) in aqueous medium; stable under natural sunlight	Simple centrifugation & filtration	Eclipse XDB C8 analytical (150 × 2.1 mm, 5 µm); water/MeOH gradient	Exactive Orbitrap HRMS; full scan on (+)ESI, DDA	Fragment-ion interpretation; retention-time separation of isomers; fluoride signature ions <i>m/z</i> 173 and 145; ≤5 ppm mass accuracy, MZmine-2.33	level 2 for most PPs; some tentative level 3 where isomeric	Stable persistence of fluorinated fragments; multiple hydroxylated TPs more polar and more mobile in water	[61]
Fluopyram (FLP)	3 TPs	F1, F2, F3	All 3 retain fluorine; F1 & F2 retain CF ₃ -pharmacophore; F3 retains CF ₃ -Ph fragment	Hydroxylation; oxidative imide formation; amide-bond cleavage	Ozone microbubble treatment (OMBT)	Direct analysis after OMBT	ACQUITY HSS T3 (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.8 µm), 0.1% aqueous formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B).	Ion trap–Orbitrap HRMS, full-scan, DDA, ESI+	Fragment interpretation; exact mass; DFT/MEP modeling; ECOSAR & T.E.S.T. toxicity prediction	level 2 for F1 & F2, level 3 for F3	F3 shows very high solubility → elevated environmental mobility; F1/F2 remain persistent	[62]
Flufenacet (FLF)	32 TPs	32 TPs grouped into mechanistic families	Many intermediate TPs retain CF ₃ -thiadiazole; later species produce CF ₃ -cleavage fragments; phenolic TPs defluorinated	Hydroxylation, dehydrogenation, alcohol oxidation to ketones, thiadiazole-ring cleavage, N-dealkylation, defluorination	Aqueous solution with TiO ₂ photocatalyst; simulated sunlight or UV	Direct liquid analysis; filtration	C18 Phenomenex Luna, (150 mm × 2.0 mm), acetonitrile/formic acid 0.05% in water	LTQ Orbitrap MS ² ; ESI+	Fragment ion analysis; neutral loss mapping; mechanistic grouping by MS ² ; retention behavior;	level 2 for major intermediates; level 3 for later-stage fragments	Numerous TPs more toxic than parent; CF ₃ group confers persistence; late-stage mineralization eliminates toxicity	[63]

mechanism-specific TPs formed under particular oxidative conditions.

Finally, for flufenacet, TiO₂-assisted photocatalytic degradation produced an extensive transformation network that was characterized using HPLC-LTQ Orbitrap [63]. A total of 32 TPs were detected, classified into mechanistic transformation families reflecting mono-/dihydroxylation, alcohol oxidation, N-dealkylation, thiadiazole-ring cleavage, and defluorination. Early-stage hydroxylated intermediates at *m/z* 380.0692 (I-A-E) dominated initial reactions, followed by oxidized keto/lactam derivatives and later-stage fragmentation products. Many intermediates retained the CF₃-thiadiazole moiety, forming persistent fluorinated residues with characteristic mass-defect features. However, unlike fluopyram, flufenacet also exhibited partial fluorine release, producing smaller phenolic fragments, including 4-fluorophenol, catechol, and phenol, indicating that not all transformation pathways preserve the fluorinated unit. This structural divergence suggests variable persistence of different molecular fragments in aquatic environments. Toxicity assays using *Vibrio fischeri* showed that several intermediates

were more toxic than the parent compound, with acute toxicity peaking mid-degradation before diminishing as the molecule underwent deeper breakdown and eventual mineralization. The studies summarized in Table 4 provide detailed HRMS datasets for transformation products (TPs), including retention time, molecular formula, theoretical and experimental *m/z*, ppm error, and diagnostic fragment ions. These data constitute high-quality spectral and structural references that can support future identification, library development, and retrospective screening in environmental analyses. Importantly, the findings also indicate that TP formation does not necessarily reduce overall toxicity, emphasizing the need for TP-aware environmental risk assessment rather than parent-compound-only evaluation.

4. Concluding remarks and future perspectives

Fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products (TPs) are environmentally persistent, analytically challenging, and under-

Fig. 3. a-b: Transformation pathways elucidated using a dual LC-HRMS approach of: a) Trifloxysulfuron (TFS), and b) Prosulfuron (PSF) during hydrolysis (pH 4 and 50 (± 0.5) °C), chlorination ($[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{T},0} = 100 \mu\text{M}$, contact time 1 h), UV photolysis (average irradiance: 0.82 mW cm^{-2}), ozonation ($0 \mu\text{M} \leq [\text{O}_3]_0 \leq 50 \mu\text{M}$) and OH radical reaction ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0 = 100 \text{ mM}$ combined with UV irradiation). All TPs were detected in ESI⁺ mode except from the PSF TPs TP284, TP268 and TP252 (Reproduced with permission of Elsevier, [61]).

identified contaminants in environmental matrices compared to other pesticide classes. While target LC–HRMS methods remain the cornerstone of regulatory monitoring, they are inherently limited to compounds with available standards, leaving many fluorinated TP's undetected. Notably, several TP's retain fluorinated moieties (e.g., –CF₃), contributing to enhanced persistence, mobility, and, in some cases, toxicity relative to their parent compounds. The occurrence of fluorinated TP's across multiple studies highlights the role of fluorination in extending environmental stability and promoting long-range transport, even at trace concentrations. Although suspect and non-target screening approaches have improved the detection of previously undetected compounds, their effectiveness depends strongly on high-quality spectral libraries, curated suspect lists, and robust data-processing workflows.

Laboratory-based transformation studies provide essential complementary insight by generating reference spectra and elucidating transformation pathways under controlled conditions, thereby improving identification confidence and reducing false positives. The integration of experimental data with *in silico* tools (e.g., mass-defect filtering, retention-time prediction, and transformation modeling) represents a promising direction for advancing fluorinated TP identification. Future progress will require the expansion of TP spectral libraries, improved standardization of screening workflows, and FAIR-compliant data sharing to enhance reproducibility and comparability across studies. Combined experimental and computational strategies will be critical for improving the monitoring and understanding of fluorinated pesticides and their transformation products in the environment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vasileios D. Alampanos: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Dimitra A. Lambropoulou:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors are unable or have chosen not to specify which data has been used.

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